

Basic Roadmap For Gender Equality By Empowering Women: A Literature Review**Umut Ahmet SEYREK^{1*}, Kürşat DEMİRYÜREK²**¹Ondokuz Mayıs Üniversitesi, Lisansüstü Eğitim Enstitüsü, Samsun²Ondokuz Mayıs Üniversitesi, Ziraat Fakültesi, Samsun¹<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3274-5894>²<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6193-9957>*chntruas@gmail.com<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8163478>**Reviews****Article History:**

Received: 2023/02/27

Accept: 2023/06/10

Available online: 2023/06/30

Keywords:

Gender Equality

Empowerment

Development

Entrepreneurship

Innovative Approach

ABSTRACT

The most important factor in ensuring social development is gender equality. It is seen that there have been many studies in the literature on gender equality, which has been tried to be shaped as a savior actor with a completely different dimension in the globalization process. But unfortunately, a concrete general roadmap that will achieve the desired goal has not been established. An international success with global value on gender equality, women's empowerment and development has not been achieved. In our study, which we have done with the awareness of this deficiency, a literature review has been made based on the idea that social and political regulations shaped on the basis of educational and cultural revolutions specific to every society that will create awareness in order to make a humane equal life possible, regardless of gender, and the need to create generally accepted road maps. In this context, the freedom of working life, which is one of the necessary inputs for women's empowerment and gender equality, and the obstacles to this have been evaluated. Entrepreneurship, which is the main theme of our study, has been seen as a solution and its serious impact on development has been discussed by drawing attention to the mistakes and deficiencies in this field. As a result, it has been tried to contribute in the light of the literature to determine a draft roadmap for ensuring gender equality by empowering women in all areas of life, especially working life, within an innovative approach that will be formed with the universal principles to be determined by the common mind in achieving social welfare.

Introduction

Policy makers, capitalists, independent academia and religious institutions of all nations should be aware that women, as a gender-free individual, have all vital, social and communal rights regarding human equality and can freely exercise their rights. In addition, it is necessary to be aware that women are free in their choices and have an equal share in equality of opportunity, and this awareness should be internalized. One of the critical stages of the human development phase will be reached when all social development approaches developed to ensure gender equality are discussed only on the basis of a philosophical doctrine that will create a human consciousness that should be adopted by all humanity. Then, the solutions to the problems that exist for women to have the freedom to work, which are an equally important part of this phase, can be discussed.

As it is known, the provision of a gender-free, libertarian and fair business life constitutes the main field of necessity for women's empowerment struggle. Empowerment includes having awareness and control in all areas of life within the social structure, being able to freely exercise and defend their rights, as well as equal participation in decision-making processes in political, social, economic, cultural and all fields, and more. The empowerment process can be secured

by universal and national policies. In a study conducted in our country, the policy areas in the relevant government action plan were examined to determine the requirements and proposals for women's empowerment, and the criteria affecting women's empowerment were discussed. (Yıldırım ve Candan, 2021). The empowerment action that can be considered for disadvantaged people who are condemned to difficulties and obstacles, as an effort identified with women, has been the concept used in national and international conventions, policies and action plans on the axis of development until today. Within the scope of this concept, it is aimed to ensure the freedom of women by increasing their opportunities on a global scale, and also to make their existence equal in social life. As we emphasized the right to freedom and choice, in the study of Goulart et al. (2021), the definition of empowerment was referred to as the process of change in one's ability to choose. Likewise, Kaaber (2021) emphasized the connection between power and preference concepts and empowerment. Regardless of gender, people should have the right to self-control of their personal life. Another important concept, freedom, is the concept that is the basis of empowerment. Freedom can be expressed as the individual's shaping his own life and directing it with free will without interference.

When evaluated in terms of women, Yıldırım ve Candan, (2021) stated in their study that women's empowerment is a multidimensional and dynamic concept that includes psychological and cognitive dimensions as well as being a process with economic, social, political and legal dimensions that enables women to realize their personalities and powers in all areas of life. Women are devalued by being forced to inequality, oppression, violence, class discrimination and poverty arising from socio-political, cultural, traditional and even religious perspectives. Empowering and emancipating women in this conflict of power and benefit, in which the male interest predominates, will be meaningful through the educational mobilization to raise awareness and the realization of political regulations and universal cooperation that will ensure equality in all areas, especially in working life. The empowerment of women and gender equality (KGCE), which is an awareness phenomenon, will carry the individual and then social welfare and development to ideal levels by developing the competencies and skills which enable them to have an equal presence, compete and have a say with self-confidence in all areas, especially in working life. In this context, the following necessities for women empowering issue to which The United Nations, (2017) draws attention “ensuring gender equality in the workplace, treating all employees fairly, non-discrimination, encouraging women in professional and professional development, ensuring the health, safety and well-being of women employees, implementing entrepreneurship, supply chain and marketing processes for women's empowerment, and ensuring the implementation” are our focusing

points. It is the essential duty of the higher mind to make the necessary arrangements for these issues.

The recipe created with knowledge, awareness and education, which will be blended by preserving the independence and transparency of politics and economics, will shape the egalitarian social revolution by ensuring the empowerment of women both individually and collectively. In support of this view, Stromquist mentioned four components of empowerment: cognition, psychology, politics, and economics (Stromquist and Nelly, 1995). Men's awareness of the value of women, accepting that they are free in their choices, not being an obstacle to equal access to opportunities and resources, getting rid of the psychology of controlling women's lives within and outside the family are the elements that will form the basis for the construction of national and international equal social life (Yıldırım ve Candan, 2021).

In this study, which is a literature review, the working life of women is evaluated in terms of occupation and wage discrimination, based on the empowerment approach, which is discussed from the perspective of gender inequality analysis. The reasons for discrimination were examined. It has been discussed whether entrepreneurship is a solution against discrimination and its contribution to development. Opinions about the three basic resources that are thought to be necessary for entrepreneurship are given, and as a result, a perspective on the importance of ensuring gender equality by empowering women has been tried to be brought.

Two Main Problems Under Gender Discrimination in Working Life: Occupation and Wage

In general, although there are positive developments in the world that the gender inequality gap in working life has begun to be eliminated numerically. It was highlighted in the 'gender differences in employment outcomes' LMF1.6 report of OECD that over the past two decades, the gender gap in employment rates almost halved, from 18% in 2000 to 10.5% in 2021 on average across OECD countries. Whether these developments are statistically significant at global, regional and national levels and whether these numerical changes make a positive change in creating a perspective of equality in consciousness and perception can be understood by international comprehensive in-depth analyzes. The general opinion seen in the literature reviews is that the representation of women in the labor market has not caught up with men.

Ingrained traditional mentality exposes women to occupational discrimination and condemns them to certain professions and sectors. For example, it is reported that only 8% of working women work in male-dominated sectors, even in Europe, which will be called the

developed continent of the world (McCaughey, 2023). So much so that women are universally pushed to a secondary position in the labor market. This unfair attitude that assigns a role to women and directs them is not only limited to sector discrimination, but also puts a glass ceiling on the career ladders at all levels of the workforce without exception. In a study on the so-called abstract glass ceiling phenomenon, which is the concrete barrier of gender discrimination in women's career development, it was found that there is a relationship between appointment and sexism and the glass ceiling disability was observed significantly. In the same study, it was emphasized that the glass ceiling, which causes inequality of opportunity in women's workforce, actually hinders national development (Nargis et. all., 2021). In an another study in which perspectives on gender-based discrimination in the labor market are discussed, it is argued that the feminist approach as an effective policy should be the starting point of gender analysis (Kılınç ve Karaçay, 2021). Compared to an opposite point of view, according to Marshall, the main task of women is to establish a healthy home life for male workers and future male workers (male children) without demanding wages in order to ensure men competent development. Therefore, he opposes the employment of married women in order to prevent them from disrupting their responsibilities in home life. The family structure, in which the traditional sexist division of labor is maintained, is the most basic and most effective economic task unit in capitalist societies. In this structure, the duty of women is to undertake domestic labor for the productivity and health of the male workforce. In the capitalist system, women are expected to sacrifice themselves for domestic labor and male employees by not participating in the workforce. According to an exemplary point of view regarding sector restrictions, which can be seen as making decisions and making choices on behalf of women within the scope of the roles assigned to women, it has been pointed out that women are deemed worthy of professions where productivity losses and costs will be low, considering the break they take from work (Koçak, 1999). For example, if the employer thinks that women will stop working for childcare in the future, they may be reluctant to raise capital for female workers (Fang and Moro, 2010). However, in today's conditions of intense volatile changable crisis, considering the short or long-term unemployment of man or interruption of man workforce for any reason, the discriminatory approach that considers women low should be criticized. When we consider discrimination from different job positions, we come across many examples (Bertogg 2020; Channar 2011; Hye-Ryun and Chris 2005). For example, it is clear that jobs that require high skills, experience and knowledge, such as high-income senior management, are still under the monopoly of men. Similarly, in an example of socks handled from the perspective of customers, it is noted that the marketing of the product by a female salesperson

is not seen as a problem, but the labor given by women in the automobile market or legal service is not desired (Kılınç ve Karaçay, 2021).

In the literature review, it has been pointed out that the decrease in the elasticity of supply of female workers will deepen the gender wage discrimination in a modeling example such as Statistical Discrimination and Monopsony regarding wages where discrimination is experienced (Bart and Olsen, 2009). Kılıç and Karaçay, (2021) state that due to gender inequality between men and women with equal efficiency, wage inequality continues to exist even in the most developed capitalist economies.

The existence of today's precariat, which may have a great impact in the future, and the ineffectiveness or absence of unions such as trade unions that can protect the rights of women who are discriminated against, within the unlawfulness and systemlessness created by the broken and changed economic and political approaches that cause serious social stalemates, pushes the problem of gender inequality in working life to become chronic. In the monopson male-dominated business world, powered by gender inequality, whatever the value of the female workforce is, the price of women labor supply becomes worthless in the exploitation of men. It should be known that the effort of men to dequalify and use women is a phenomenon that dishonors human qualities, not only with the definition of gender discrimination, but also as human inequality. The fact that women and their labor cannot be positioned and devalued in the digitalized world, where class changes take place accordingly, further enlarges and deepens this human discrimination. To put it simply, the power of the male workforce in all sectors marginalizes women who offer unpaid labor such as housework and restricts their vital rights. Hartmann referred to the struggle needed to stop capitalism that exploits women's labor both inside and outside the home (Hartman, 1992).

Is female entrepreneurship the solution?

There is an increasing interest in the concept of women's entrepreneurship against unemployment, economic dependence, inequality and all women's labor problems. Since the 1980s, many countries have chosen to abandon the social state understanding by reducing public expenditures and reducing public employment with the liberal economic policies they have implemented. As a result, tools such as loans for entrepreneurship incentives and tax reductions were introduced as a solution to the increasing unemployment problem. New models and methods have been tried to increase women's entrepreneurship. Encouraging policies regarding women's entrepreneurship have been initiated by international organizations such as the European Union (EU), World Bank (WB) and United Nations Development Program (UNDP) (Sallan Gül and Altındal, 2016). Entrepreneurial activity, which gained

serious importance, was seen as a means of prosperity, innovation and change and was associated with the success of the universalization process (Kaygın ve Güven, 2014). In developing countries, entrepreneurship has been perceived as the main factor that will shape the market strongly and realize development (Mwangi, 2012).

In today's evolving political and economic conjuncture, the importance and value of women's presence in working life has been seriously felt in reference to the demographic changes of the workable population. Developments such as industry 4.0 and 5.0, especially in the service sector, have almost triggered the entrepreneurship of women in digitally integrated jobs (Ughetto et. all., 2020). Many entrepreneurial women at different educational levels, who are role models in this regard, set an example. However, the share of women in business life, both as an entrepreneurship and as a workforce, is far behind that of men. We can see such data in the world bank and Global Entrepreneurship Monitor data. Women who do not get their fair share face economic problems more severely. As it is known, women who are exposed to gender inequality and discrimination in socio-cultural and other fields are most severely affected by poverty. Considering the inequalities between women and men around the world, it can be thought that studies on entrepreneurship in the context of women's empowerment and gender equality are not yet at a sufficient stage and multidimensional in-depth studies should be done. When we consider the subject in our country, there are various studies in the literature in which the subject of women's entrepreneurship is evaluated from different perspectives and approaches with different dimensions. For example, in a study conducted, women's entrepreneurship was examined from two different perspectives that it could be used as a tool against low employment and poverty. In this context, it was aimed to encourage women to become employers, to transition them to an income-generating form other than paid work, and to build profitable sustainability by establishing businesses through trainings on this subject. Likewise, from the secondary approach, entrepreneurial activity was accepted as a tool to raise family welfare and cure poverty (Sallan Gül and Altındal, 2016). Topateş et al. (2022) emphasized that the neoliberal policies that provide cheap labor to global capital have led to the deepening of women's poverty and emphasized that the empowerment approach to women's entrepreneurship, which will be a solution to women's problems in economic and social dimensions, has gained importance. Kaaber, (2005) has mentioned three dimensions: resources, tools and achievements that are essential in women's empowerment work. In another related study, seven basic features required for women's empowerment are mentioned; to participate in decision-making mechanisms, to have control over household resources, to gain entrepreneurial qualities, to be respected by the spouse and society, to be helped by the spouse

in household obligations, to have the ability to decide on expenditures and to have the freedom to use their own time (Makombe, 2006). Entrepreneurship, which is one of these features and is now directly associated with the empowerment of women, is perceived as the solution to the basic problem. Again, in the article of Topateş et al. (2022), the statement "Traditional gender roles that prevent women from participating in employment as entrepreneurs make it difficult for them to become economically and socially empowered, showing the correlation between women's entrepreneurship and empowerment" supports our argument.

Ways to Strengthen Women's Entrepreneurship: Microcredits, Financing, Cooperatives as Forces

A wide range of supports and resources are required to encourage women's entrepreneurship, to increase the number of entrepreneurs and to ensure that they have an equal share in the sectors. An example tool that emphasizes the need to be used as a resource for women's entrepreneurship is microcredit, which has discussions on its importance and inadequacy in the fight against poverty in the literature. In this context, the relationship between women's poverty and microcredit was tested in a Turkey study using the symmetric causality test. According to the results, it was found that there is no causality between the level of microcredit used and the decrease in women's poverty. and it is predicted that the effect of informal institutions on gender and the inadequacy of education level are determinants in the emergence of these results (Çuhadar ve Algan, 2019). It has been evaluated that the use of micro credit, which was discussed at the Women's Entrepreneurship Summit, is seen as a contribution to the family budget for women entrepreneurs, and the income obtained is spent to meet the needs of their families instead of the enterprise. However, since women's entrepreneurship is perceived as a form of employment rather than entrepreneurship in the current approach, it has not been able to lift women out of poverty despite the increase in the number of women working on their behalf (The World Bank, 1998).

Financing supports need to be considered more comprehensively than existing instruments. Another important issue that will be a resource for women's entrepreneurship via to the empowerment of women is the financial policies of the public that will protect and support women. Because women entrepreneurs in developing countries are motivated by economic factors to take initiatives (Sağlamyürek, 2021). For example, specially planned budgets need to be created for entrepreneurship and other social education for disadvantaged women. Especially in rural areas, towns, underdeveloped regions and cities with low population, cultural richness can be integrated with tourism. lost or disappearing crafts can be revived. Thus, the allocation of financial opportunities that will bring related professional

groups to women's entrepreneurship and create employment will provide benefits. At this point, the point to be considered is not to cause women to be restricted only to micro-scale low-value simple jobs such as traditional home production. In a study conducted by Filizöz and Yaraş, (2020) in the TR72 region, it was determined that most of the women entrepreneurs are engaged in entrepreneurial activities in jobs that are seen suitable for women (restaurant management, clothing stores, home cooking business, etc.) and in service sectors (hairdresser, beauty salon, etc.) aimed at meeting women's needs, rather than the industrial sector. In support of these findings, in another study examining the years 2012-2020, it was determined that the majority of women entrepreneurs owned sole proprietorships in the form of small organizations instead of large enterprises that included extensive organizational activities. In other words, it has been determined that most of the women entrepreneurs in Turkey are involved in the wholesale and retail sector. The sectors with the highest number of initiatives are accommodation, food and service sectors. It was observed that 31026 of the women entrepreneurs supported by KOSGEB in the said years were members of the Chamber of Craftsmen. It has been determined that the chamber of commerce is in the second place, and the least membership is seen in the chamber of maritime commerce with 20 people and the chamber of industry with 35 people (Sağlamyürek, 2021). In other words, the point that needs to be emphasized is not to make the mistake of keeping women distracted with narrow-scoped jobs that lack the entrepreneurial spirit, do not need development and innovation, and do not require advanced training. In a study that seems to summarize our evaluations, it has been stated that instead of aiming for women to gain economic independence in the entrepreneurship process, they are supported by micro-credits and entrepreneurial trainings in small businesses with simple organizational structures (Sallan Gül ve Altındal, 2016). Although women's entrepreneurship was supported against so-called gender inequality, their clustering in a basket containing certain sectors and business structures could not be prevented due to the glass walls they encountered in front of sectoral development and growth opportunities. System, approach and organizational structures that will enable women to become effective independent individuals who have a say in entrepreneurship, is decision maker, is sought after, have high competitive power, by gaining skills, competence, experience and receiving the necessary training in an equal and liberal system needs to be developed. In this context, cooperatives can be reconsidered in an innovative way as an exemplary structure that will provide all the necessities, protect the rights, and empower women to achieve their goals and achievements in a holistic power cooperation. A case study concluded that economic independence through cooperatives helps women gain control over resources and empowers women (Bharti, 2021).

According to one view, women's cooperatives are seen as a critical structure in the empowerment process by providing significant contributions to women's empowerment, providing equal access to economic and social resources that women are disadvantaged and deprived of with basic objectives such as increasing employment, reducing poverty, inclusion of women in social and economic life (Karakuş, 2022). According to the results of the research survey in the same study, it was stated that cooperative members earn better, their living standards improve, they can produce and market more effectively, they have more positive personality perceptions, they have the right to be a decision maker and they assume leadership roles (Karakuş, 2022).

Combating Stereotypes and the Development Impact of Women's Entrepreneurship

In line with the empowerment approach, an important issue as a tool to support women's entrepreneurship is the provision of social guarantees for women entrepreneurs on issues such as child assistance, health care and bankruptcy, as realized in social democratic welfare regimes. In addition to these, policies should be developed within the scope of effective struggle against social deprivations and disadvantages such as “Discrimination by government agencies, customers, suppliers”, “being ignored by business contacts or colleagues”, “difficulties in finding effective funds”, “deprivation of support from family and friends”, “not getting good advice from government agencies and banks” (Still, 2005).

At the heart of all the problems, deprivations and limitations stemming from gender inequality that puts women at a disadvantage is the fact that the stereotypes in mind against women have not been broken. According to Tereškinas, cited in Bayat and Baykal's study (2021), multidimensional stereotypes about gender roles are imposed on people from childhood and people are brought up and educated with these versatile stereotypes. Women cannot be active in every field in their life and in the society, and they cannot realize their potential by always being stuck in constraints, because of the belief that women do not have the skills and competencies to adapt to changes; their leadership skills are limited compared to men; they do not have the courage to take initiative; they are labeled as masculine women even if they take the initiative; their professions are designed according to men; and many women deserve the second role (Aalito, 2008).

However, highly competitive internationalized women's entrepreneurship may be initiating the opportunistic economic currents of the new industrial revolution. It is obvious that the development of women's entrepreneurship has serious effects on economic transformation and development at macro and micro levels. It is known to have positive

benefits such as creating employment at the macro level, developing innovative technologies and innovation, and contributing to the gross national product (Armour and Enriques, 2018). At the micro level, it has been mentioned that women participating in entrepreneurial activities through the redistribution and diversification of income contribute to their individual and domestic socio-economic development, creating jobs in various sectors and improving their financial assets (Cassar, 2014).

Despite this, in the fight against women's poverty and entrepreneurship problems, it is necessary not to put the issue only in the narrow mold of development. Development and prosperity will be one of the universal humane final positive results that will be ultimately brought by women's employment, empowerment and independence. While capital's exploitation of women and patriarchal control pressure on women's domestic and foreign labor creates a kind of profitability in the labor-capital relationship, it ensures the progress of production relations at a level where "empowerment" and "opportunity" strategies are excluded. In this sense, it is essential for policy makers to consider women who are condemned to subordinate positions within the scope of empowerment and opportunity components (Nusbaum, 1999).

Discussion

Is it the right way to ensure gender equality by empowering women? Or is it the right way to empower women by ensuring gender equality?

In order for the development plans designed within the framework of gender equality to be implemented, it is essential that the real contributions of women, which cannot be ignored, be consciously adopted and accepted, primarily in the realization of social development and welfare. In this context, a development without the actual contribution of women is neither sustainable nor realistic. According to the conclusion of the researches, there is a linear relationship between the level of development of the country and the level of gender inequality (Toksöz, 2011). According to Ostergaard, (1992) it is essential that those who design development plans be mindful of extreme conflicts. Afterwards, since development is a multi-faceted process, a human-centered approach should be adopted instead of bureaucratic. Ultimately, the development move should be analyzed holistically, covering the entire population within gender equality. Therefore, policies made indirectly by ignoring the phenomenon that only considers human as singular from a masculine framework, in other words, imprisoning women in roles deemed appropriate for him in the social life dominated by men, cannot achieve ultimate success in the struggle for gender inequality in line with development goals. The persistence of gender inequality in different forms and levels at the international level is proof of this (Kılınç ve Karaçay, 2021). For this reason, an international

unity initiative should be established. In the fight against gender inequality, first of all, a universal common mind and will must be established. The basic elements consisting of a direct single package, which is determined within the framework of awareness in its psychological aspect, eliminates the differences, and which is revealed as a result of multi-dimensional analyzes by considering the issue as genderless, should be put into action as the 'Universal Empowered Woman' model. For example, the common aspects that Balkız and Öztürk, (2013) point out about the empowerment of women are participation in the decision-making process, equality, political power acquisition, rights and self-respect.

In order to strengthen the position of women in all areas of global and social life and to prevent gender discrimination, joint new policies and strategies should be developed and action plans that are secure and deterrent against negativities should be activated within the framework of cooperation by considering international relations. In order to strengthen and equalize women's social positions and to increase their direct independent and unhindered participation in the development process, the improving their status in the areas of basic rights and freedoms such as education, health, employment and social security, and making legal arrangements against the problems that hinder gender equality will make human development progress possible. All these evaluations can be described with the following statements of Lober, to whom Kılıç and Karaçay, (2021) refer: “Gender inequality against women is not a temporary or individual problem; This inequality lies deep within social structures. Gender-based inequalities are built within the family, the labor market, the political arena, religious belief, cultural activities, and spoken language.

Within the scope of entrepreneurship and empowerment, which is one of the branches of the transformation that will occur within the framework of gender equality in the patriarchal social structure and which constitutes the universe of our work, policy makers, capital owners, independent academia and religious institutions and international organizations are need to develop common elements in terms of empowering women entrepreneurs in terms of economic, social, political and communication network. For example, in a study, it was concluded that communicative networks support women's entrepreneurship and increase business success (Demirel ve Bakırtaş, 2022). It is reported that practices promoting entrepreneurship are clearly effective in preventing women's unemployment and poverty in developing countries (De Vita et.al. 2014). However, in the context of cultural values, behaviors and pressures, it is seen that the serious obstacles that still exist in front of women's entrepreneurial activities cannot be completely removed (Mungai and Ogot, 2012). The basic recipe for the economic independence and empowerment of women entrepreneurs is to bring

gender equality closer to the ideal level, based on studies such as gaining skills and competence through education, disseminating technology learning, gaining experience and courage, preventing physical, psychological and sexual violence, and removing all socio-cultural barriers.

The empowerment of women on the basis of gender equality and the integration of women in development is a starting point for economic and social inclusion. Seçkin and Meşe, (2021) said: “Similar to the global trends, entrepreneurship in Turkey was considered as the locomotive of the economy, associated with growth/regional development, and the male-dominated characteristics and characters attributed to the entrepreneur and entrepreneurship were accepted as the norm and developed within the framework of how far women are from these norms”. Since women are not allowed to access the aforementioned norm limits, they are imprisoned in limited entrepreneurship. So much so that, similar to the situation experienced by many countries, the concept of women's entrepreneurship in Turkey has been supported within the scope of small business initiatives in line with the policies developed to eliminate unemployment and prevent poverty, beyond the self-employment of women (Sallan Gül ve Altındal, 2016). Women who want to own a small business within the limits and levels drawn to their abilities according to the roles assigned to them, generally engage in entrepreneurship to provide an additional income for the home economy. According to various research findings in the literature and the data of statistical institutions, it is seen that most of the women are engaged in entrepreneurial activities in the service and retail sector rather than the manufacturing industry (OECD/European Union, 2017). It is clear that the experience, knowledge, technology and capital requirements required in the service and retail sectors are quite low compared to the manufacturing industry. Therefore, women who have limited work experience, insufficient business and management education and many other deprivations are stuck in concepts such as glass ceiling, sticky floor, glass elevator, glass cliff, glass wall which are reflections of disadvantaged situations, or they have to adapt (Bayat ve Baykal, 2021). Women who cannot overcome their stuck positions cannot advance in their careers, they almost cling to the base of the structures they are in, they are crushed under heavy responsibilities during their working life, they hesitate or regress due to inequalities of opportunity and obstacles to development opportunities, and worse, they have to leave working life. As if all these barriers are insufficient, women struggle with male competition even in professions deemed suitable for them or they may encounter obstacles by their fellows.

The problems faced by women in working life, which is their basic right in the struggle for survival, are so intense and deep that it is not correct to resort to temporary methods instead

of focusing on structural factors in the solution of these problems. It is wrong for different decision-making and guiding actors to implement different strategies to support women's entrepreneurship in line with their differing goals. Attrition of the phenomenon of entrepreneurship and diversion of entrepreneurship from its purpose through empirical practices in scattered and different forms harms the empowerment of women as a social policylessness.

Result and Suggestions

In order to ensure and sustain gender equality by empowering women, the situations and positions of women and men entrepreneurs in their culture should be analyzed in depth. According to the analysis, realistic strategies and plans produced by the common mind and will should be determined. In the context of empowerment, superior opportunities for women should be defined. All social, political, economic and legal arrangements should be made in order to transform the potentials of women entrepreneurs into successful results. The introduction of role models should be made more effective. Access to finance, which is one of the most important resource elements of women's entrepreneurship, should be facilitated and supports should be made more efficient. Necessary effective support should be provided for the growth of existing enterprises. Cooperatives or alternative new unions need to be developed. In the new age of digital revolution, women's technology learning should be carried out. Services and projects should be developed in medium and high technology sectors that will appeal to target groups that integrate entrepreneurship with innovation, and women should be fully integrated into these areas. It should be ensured that women entrepreneurs gain knowledge and skills in the fields of globalization, international trade, marketing, management and law. Simple and structurally oriented universal approaches that are free from bureaucratic complexity should be developed.

It should be known that in nations where women entrepreneurs are more, employment, individual and social welfare, economic growth and development are increasing (Sağlamyürek, 2021). For all these suggestions and more, of course, trainings should be carried out to ensure that social, cultural and religious attitudes are compatible with women's business or entrepreneurship. In this case, the most effective approach that will eliminate discrimination in many issues such as profession and wages, and ensure that women are empowered in all areas of social life, is to ensure gender equality by empowering women with the universal principles to be determined by the common mind. It is thought that the first step on this path should be raising awareness.

Conflict of Interest

The authors have declared that that there are no competing interests.

References

- Aalito L., 2008. "Entrepreneurship in Organization: Gender and Social Capital", Kyrö, P. and Sundin, E. (ed.) in *Women Entrepreneurship and Social Capital: A Dialogue and Construction*, Koge, Portland, Abingdon: Copenhagen Business School Press, 23-39.
- Armour J, Enríques L., 2018. The Promise and Perils of Crowdfunding: between Corporate Finance and Consumer Contracts. *Modern Law Review*, 81(1): 51-84.
- Balkız I, Öztürk E., 2013. Neo-liberal Gelişme Anlayışı ve Kadın: Mikrofinans Uygulamaları Kadınları Güçlendiriyor Mu?, *Mediterranean Journal of Humanities*, 3(2): 1-21.
- Bart E, Olsen H.D., 2009. Monopsonistic Discrimination, Worker Turnover, And The Gender Wage Gap. *Labour Economics*, 16: 589–597.
- Bayat İ, Baykal B., 2021. Toplumsal Cinsiyet Ayrımcılığının Yarattığı Engeller: Çalışma Yaşamında Varılmaya Çalışan Kadın. *Ankara Hacı Bayram Veli Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 23 (3): 745-762.
- Bharti N., 2021. Role of cooperatives in economic empowerment of women: a review of Indian experiences. *World Journal of Entrepreneurship, Management and Sustainable Development*. 17(4): 617-631.
- Bertogg A, Imdorf C, Hyggen C. et al., 2020. Gender Discrimination in the Hiring of Skilled Professionals in Two Male-Dominated Occupational Fields: A Factorial Survey Experiment with Real-World Vacancies and Recruiters in Four European Countries. *Köln Z Soziol* 72 (Suppl 1): 261–289.
- Cassar G., 2014. Industry and Startup Experience on Entrepreneur Forecast Performance in New Firms. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 29(1): 137-151.
- Channar Z A, Abbassi Z, Ujan I A., 2011. Gender discrimination in workforce and its impact on the employees, *Pakistan Journal of Commerce and Social Sciences (PJCSS)*, 5 (1), 177-191.
- Çuhadar P, Algan N., 2019. Kadın Yoksulluğu ve Mikro Kredi: Türkiye Üzerine Ampirik Bir İnceleme. *Marmara Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Dergisi*, 41(1): 83-105.
- De Vita L, Mari M, Poggesi S., 2014. Women Entrepreneurs in and from Developing Countries: Evidences from the Literature. *European Management Journal*, 32(3): 451-460.
- Demirel Z H, Bakırtaş H., 2022. İş Hayatında Kadınların Güçlendirilmesi ve Aile İlişisine Etkisi. *Alanya Akademik Bakış*, 6(3): 3129-315.

- Fang H, Moro A., 2010. Theories of Statistical Discrimination and Affirmative Action: A Survey. Edited: Jess Benhabib, Alberto Bisin, Matthew O. Jackson, Handbook of Social Economics, p.133-200. Elsevier.
- Farhat A, Nargis A, Uzma A., 2021. Glass Ceiling Effect and Women Career: Determining factors in Higher Education Institutions. SJESR, 4: 1–8.
- Filizöz B, Yaraş D., 2020. Kadın Girişimci Profilinin Belirlenmesine Yönelik TR72 Bölgesinde Bir Araştırma. Girişimcilik İnovasyon ve Pazarlama Araştırmaları Dergisi, 4(8): 179-196.
- Goulart C.M, Purewal A, Nakhuda H. et al., 2021. Tools for measuring gender equality and women’s empowerment (GEWE) indicators in humanitarian settings. Confl Health 15, 39.
- Hartman H., 1992. Marksizmle Feminizmin Mutsuz Evliliği. Derleyen: Gülnur,A. Savran , Nesrin, T. Demiryontan. Kadının Görünmeyen Emeği, 157-187. İstanbul: Kardelen Yayınları
- Hye-Ryun K, Chris R., 2005. Women in Management in South Korea: Advancement or Retrenchment?, Asia Pacific Business Review, 11(2): 213-231.
- Kabeer N., 2001. Conflicts over Credit: Reevaluating the Empowerment Potential of Loans to Women in Rural Bangladesh. World Development, 29(1), 63–84.
- Kabeer N., 2005. Gender equality and women’s empowerment: A critical analysis of the third millenium development goal 1. Gender and Development, 13(1): 13-24.
- Kalfa Topateş A, Topateş H, Kıdak E., 2022. Güçlendirme ve Toplumsal Cinsiyet Rollerini İkiliminde Kadın Girişimciliği. Çalışma ve Toplum, 2(73): 1043-1074.
- Karakuş G., 2022. Kadın Kooperatiflerinin Kadınların Güçlendirilmesi ve Toplumsal Cinsiyet Eşitliğinin Sağlanmasındaki Rolü. Pamukkale Üniversitesi İşletme Araştırmaları Dergisi, 9(1): 247-259.
- Kaygın E, Güven B., 2014. Kadın Girişimcilik: Farklı Boyutlarıyla. Veritas akademi.
- Kılınç N, Karaçay H., 2021. İşgücü Piyasasında Kadının Konumu ve Cinsiyete Dayalı Ayrımcılık: Neoklasik ve Marksist Yaklaşımlar Üzerine Bir Değerlendirme. Journal of International Management Educational and Economics Perspectives, 9(1): 24-33.
- Koçak S., 1999. Gender Discrimination in The Turkish Labour Market. Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences at the De Montfort University. Yayınlanmamış Doktora Tezi.
- Makombe I. A. M., 2006. Women Entrepreneurship Development and Empowerment in Tanzania: The Case of SIDO-UNIDO-Supported Women Microentrepreneurs in the Food Processing Sector, Development Studies at the University of South Africa.

- McCaughey M., 2023. Separate and unequal: Gender segregation at work. Social Europe. (<https://www.socialeurope.eu/separate-and-unequal-gender-segregation-at-work>)
- Mungaı E.N., Ogot M., 2012. Gender, Culture and Entrepreneurship in Kenya. *International Business Research*, 5(5): 175–183.
- Mwangi S. M., 2012. Psychosocial challenges facing female entrepreneurs in rural informal sector and their coping mechanisms: A case study of Gucha District, Kenya. *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(2): 15-27.
- Nusbaum M., 1999. Women and Equality: The Capabilities Approach. *International Labour Review*, 138(3): 227-245.
- Ostergaard L., 1992. “Gender”, Ostergaard, L. (ed.) *Gender and Development: A Practical Guide*, London: Routledge, 1-10.
- Sağlamyürek D, Taşdemir S., 2021. Sosyo-Ekonomik Kalkınmada Kadın Girişimciler ve İşletmeleri. *Girişimcilik ve Kalkınma Dergisi*, 16(2): 76-90.
- Sallan Gül S, Altındal Y., 2016. Türkiye’de Kadın Girişimciliğinin Serüveni: Başarı Mümkün mü? *Süleyman Demirel Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 21(4): 1361-1377.
- Seçkin Halaç D, Meşe G., 2021. Toplumsal Cinsiyet Bakış Açısından Türkiye’de Kadın Girişimciliğinin Durumu. *Dumlupınar Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, (68): 255-270.
- Still L. V., 2005. “The Constraints Facing Women Entering Small Business Ownership”, Fielden, S. L. and Davidson, M. C. (eds.) in *International Handbook of Women and Small Business Entrepreneurship*, Cheltenham, Northampton: Edward Elgar Publishing, 55-66.
- Stromquist Nelly P., 1995. Theoretical and Practical Bases for Empowerment, in C. Medel-Annonuevo (Ed.) *Women, Education and Empowerment: pathways towards autonomy*. Hamburg: UNESCO-UIE.
- Toksöz G., 2011. *Kalkınmada Kadın Emeği*, İstanbul: Varlık Yayınları.
- Ughetto E, Rossi M, Audretsch D. et al., 2020. Female entrepreneurship in the digital era. *Small Bus Econ*, 55: 305–312.
- United Nations, 2017. *Kadının Güçlenmesi Prensipleri (WEPs) Uygulama Rehberi*. [https://www.globalcompactturkiye.org/wpcontent/uploads/2019/01/WEPs_Rehber.pdf]
- WB The World Bank, 1998. *Gender, Using Microcredit To Advance Women*, Prem Notes, November, Number 8, pp.1-4.

Yıldırım S, Candan G., 2021. Kadının Güçlenmesine Etki Eden Kriterler Üzerinden Politika Önceliklendirmeye Yönelik Nicel Bir Yaklaşım. Yönetim ve Çalışma Dergisi. 5(2): 119-136.

<https://genderdata.worldbank.org/data-stories/flfp-data-story/>

<https://www.gemconsortium.org/reports/womens-entrepreneurship>

<https://www.oecd.org/cfe/smes/Policy-Brief-on-Women-s-Entrepreneurship.pdf>